

EMERGENCY CARE FOR FOREIGN BODY OBSTRUCTION OF THE UPPER AIRWAY IN CHILDREN

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Abstract. *Foreign body obstruction of the upper airway (FBOUA) in children is one of the most critical emergency situations requiring immediate intervention. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), aspiration of foreign objects accounts for approximately 7% of all deaths among children under the age of 5. Despite advancements in medical techniques, the issue of foreign body aspiration in children remains highly relevant. Reports of diagnostic errors and fatal outcomes associated with this serious condition continue to emerge. Changes in social living conditions, behavior, and children's lifestyles have introduced new types of foreign objects and mechanisms of aspiration.*

Keywords: *children, emergency care, airway, foreign body, obstruction, asphyxia.*

Relevance. Foreign body obstruction of the upper airway (FBOUA) in children is among the most dangerous emergencies requiring immediate intervention [3,11]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), foreign body aspiration accounts for approximately 7% of all deaths among children under the age of 5. Anatomical features of pediatric airways, such as their narrow lumen and underdeveloped protective reflexes, contribute to the high incidence of such cases [14,18,22].

Research shows that upper airway obstruction occurs significantly more frequently in children than in adults [1,4,21]. Moreover, the approaches to providing emergency care to children in these situations differ significantly from those used for adult patients.

Saving a child's life in cases of severe airway obstruction depends largely on how quickly and accurately bystanders can recognize the problem and provide first aid (FA). However, due to a lack of awareness and insufficient practical skills, such interventions are rarely attempted [2,4]. Although clear protocols for providing assistance exist, high mortality rates and the frequency of complications emphasize the need for further development of diagnostic methods and educational programs for both the general public and healthcare professionals [7,10].

The aim of this study is to analyze current scientific data on the principles and approaches to providing first aid for airway obstruction in children due to foreign body aspiration and to study the clinical features of this condition.

The majority of cases of foreign body airway obstruction (FBAO) in children (57-75%) occur in children under the age of three [16, 17]. This is primarily due to anatomical and physiological characteristics, such as the absence of molar teeth and insufficient chewing skills development [3, 16]. In children, the distance from the teeth to the vocal cords is shorter than in adults, which increases the risk of aspiration. According to Bruynings [12,23], this distance averages 14 cm in adult males, while in infants under one year of age, it is only 8 cm. Additionally, children under the age of two lack molars, complicating the chewing process. Contributing factors to aspiration include poor self-regulation during chewing and a weaker ability to suppress the cough reflex compared to adults [16,28].

Young children, exploring their environment, often interact with various objects and frequently introduce them into their airways. As a result, airway obstruction in children can be caused not only by food but also by other objects, such as toys. For example, one of the leading causes of fatal FBAO is latex balloons [18,24].

Due to the high incidence of FBAO in children, sudden onset of dyspnea, respiratory distress, or loss of consciousness without an apparent cause should raise suspicion of airway obstruction [19,25]. According to data [14,21], 12.6% of patients in their first year of life among all cases of foreign body airway obstruction are admitted to hospitals. Infants form a distinct group due to the severity of clinical progression, diagnostic difficulties, and the risk of rapid development of complications.

The most common causes of foreign body aspiration include food fragments (nuts, seeds, pieces of vegetables and fruits) – 45%, toys and building set parts – 30%, office items (pen caps, buttons) – 15%, and other objects such as coins and batteries – 10%. The main predisposing factors are inadequate adult supervision, hurried eating, or active play during meals [10,27].

The clinical picture of obstruction typically includes sudden coughing (88%), dyspnea and inspiratory stridor (72%), cyanosis (60%), and loss of consciousness in severe cases (12%) [18]. Foreign body aspiration in children can occur under various circumstances, such as during meals, active play, coughing, or a sudden fright, and is accompanied by specific symptoms. A sudden coughing fit, difficulty breathing, severe cyanosis, and loss of consciousness can occur even in the context of apparent well-being. These symptoms may be accompanied by reflex vomiting caused by irritation of the airways [2,26].

Coughing and dyspnea in such cases may temporarily decrease, but stenoic breathing and residual coughing persist, their severity depending on the size and location of the foreign body [19,22]. Classic symptoms of lower airway foreign bodies (LAFB) include sharp coughing and dyspnea, dull percussion sounds, and diminished breath sounds on the affected side. Radiological examination can reveal indirect signs such as atelectasis, emphysema, or mediastinal shift. However, in some cases, the clinical picture may be atypical, complicating timely diagnosis [4, 20].

In the early stages after foreign body aspiration, symptoms such as vocal cord spasm, leading to respiratory distress, cyanosis of the face and limbs, copious tearing and salivation, and small amounts of blood in sputum may develop [18, 11]. These findings highlight the importance of a thorough medical history and clinical examination for the timely detection of foreign body aspiration, particularly in the absence of typical symptoms.

The time frame for providing emergency care in such situations is strictly limited – 4-5 minutes. In essence, every parent and other caregivers should be well-informed about emergency procedures for foreign body-induced asphyxia [15,27]. Fatal FBAO usually occurs in the presence of witnesses [5]. Timely execution of simple first aid (FA) procedures by witnesses has proven effectiveness [6] and has a significant positive impact on the outcome of this critical condition [13, 20]. In contrast, delays in FA reduce the chances of survival for patients with severe FBAO. The likelihood of removing a foreign body from the airway decreases over time due to progressive airway edema and the suppression of the victim's own active attempts to expel the foreign body [15,21].

In young children, a 1-mm narrowing of the airway lumen due to edema results in a 50% reduction in airflow [1, 4, 5]. To date, there remains confusion in medical literature regarding the

division of the respiratory system into upper and lower "levels". In domestic literature, the boundary between the upper and lower respiratory tracts is considered to be the larynx [2, 7]. In American medical practice, this boundary is drawn at the level of the 5th-6th tracheal rings, which is more practical from a clinical perspective [3, 6, 11, 13, 17]. It is widely accepted that acute stenosing laryngotracheitis is an obstruction of the upper respiratory tract, involving both the subglottic space of the larynx and the upper portion of the trachea [9, 10, 12].

Direct laryngoscopy allows visualization of key anatomical structures of the airways: the entrance to the cervical esophagus and the vocal cords, which have a triangular shape and are covered by the epiglottis. Under certain conditions, such as talking, laughing, crying, or a deep inhalation during meals, solid or semi-solid food fragments (e.g., meat, candy, grapes) may be directed by the airflow towards the vocal cords. This can lead to complete obstruction and cause acute asphyxiation [20].

Anatomical features contributing to obstruction include:

- The relatively small size of the vocal cords in children, increasing the risk of complete airway closure by foreign bodies.

- The physiological tendency to aspirate due to underdeveloped swallowing and chewing skills.

It is important to note that upper airway obstruction in young children can be caused not only by foreign bodies but also by infections such as epiglottitis or croup. In such cases, the approach to care significantly differs, requiring priority pharmacological treatment and ensuring airway patency [8,28].

These findings emphasize the need for strict monitoring of children during meals and raising parental awareness about the risks of aspiration.

In pediatric patients, the narrowest part of the airway, which is prone to trauma during intubation, is the subglottic space. Post-intubation laryngeal stenosis is divided into early and late types based on their timing. Early laryngeal stenoses, occurring immediately after extubating, are dangerous due to the potential development of pulmonary edema. Therefore, early post-intubation stenoses should not be routinely considered as a result of laryngospasm [5, 11].

In countries where educational programs are widely implemented, the incidence of asphyxia syndrome in children has decreased by 85% [10,24]. In most countries, however, parents are largely unaware of the basics of prevention and emergency care for such situations.

Additionally, caregivers in kindergartens, school teachers, and staff in restaurants and cafes lack foundational knowledge on this issue. This problem requires a detailed analysis of clinical data, current diagnostic and treatment methods, as well as the development of effective educational programs for parents and healthcare personnel. All outpatient clinics and hospital departments must have the necessary equipment for performing laryngoscopy and removing foreign bodies in both children and adults who are experiencing asphyxiation due to upper airway obstruction [3, 12].

Airway obstruction in children remains a serious medical problem requiring a comprehensive approach. Timely diagnosis, knowledge of first aid protocols, and the adoption of modern technologies can significantly reduce mortality and improve the prognosis for children with this condition.

The ongoing prevalence of foreign body aspiration and the identified epidemiological features dictate the need for improving the organization of care, enhancing diagnostic and

treatment methods for patients with bronchial foreign bodies, and increasing public awareness regarding child care.

In conclusion, it should be noted that nearly all authors studying the outcome of this sudden complication emphasize its extreme danger and dramatic nature. The time for providing emergency care in such situations is strictly limited – 4-5 minutes.

Upper airway obstruction by a foreign body is a common cause of life-threatening conditions in children that require immediate intervention. Timely recognition of symptoms and the application of first aid protocols significantly improve the prognosis. It is necessary to enhance educational efforts among parents and emergency personnel to reduce the risk of fatal outcomes. The development of clear diagnostic and treatment algorithms can reduce the risk of complications and mortality.

REFERENCES

1. Гриневич В.В., Андреев А.И. Первая помощь при аспирации инородных тел у детей. *Российский педиатрический журнал*. 2021;19(5):45–50.
2. Хромов С.П., Иванова Л.В. Роль ранней диагностики в лечении обструкции дыхательных путей у детей. *Медицина неотложных состояний*. 2022;18(3):25–32.
3. Исакова А.Н., Кузнецова Т.А. Алгоритмы неотложной помощи при аспирации инородных тел у детей. *Современная педиатрия*. 2023;15(3):78–84.
4. Smith J., Brown P. Pediatric Foreign Body Aspiration: Diagnosis and Management. *Journal of Pediatric Emergency Medicine*. 2023;45(3):123–130.
5. Chen Y., et al. Clinical Features of Airway Obstruction by Foreign Bodies in Children. *Pediatrics International*. 2022;64(5):345–352.
6. Morrow S.L., et al. Advances in Bronchoscopic Management of Pediatric Airway Obstruction. *Clinical Pediatric Medicine*. 2021;48(4):567–578.
7. Bamber A.R., Pryce J., Ashworth M., Sebire N.J. Fatal aspiration of foreign bodies in infants and children. *Fetal Pediatr. Pathol*. 2014; 33 (1): 42–8.7. World Health Organization. *Global Burden of Pediatric Foreign Body Aspiration*. Geneva: WHO Press; 2021.
8. Patel N., et al. Bronchoscopic Removal of Airway Foreign Bodies in Children: A Systematic Review. *International Journal of Pediatrics*. 2022;52(1):23–35.
9. Kiyohara K, Sakai T, Nishiyama C, Nishiuchi T, Hayashi Y, Iwami T, et al. Epidemiology of Out-of-Hospital Cardiac Arrest Due to Suffocation Focusing on Suffocation Due to Japanese Rice Cake: A PopulationBased Observational Study from the Utstein Osaka Project. *J Epidemiol*. 2018;28(2):67–74. PMID: 29093354 <https://doi.org/10.2188/jea.JE20160179>
10. Wu WS, Sung KC, Cheng TJ, Lu TH. Associations between chronic diseases and choking deaths among older adults in the USA: a crosssectional study using multiple cause mortality data from 2009 to 2013. *BMJ Open*. 2015;5(11):e009464. PMID: 26563213 <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2015-009464>
11. Pavitt MJ, Nevett J, Swanton LL, Hind MD, Polkey MI, Green M, et al. London ambulance source data on choking incidence for the calendar year 2016: an observational study. *BMJ Open Respir Res*. 2017;4(1): e000215. PMID: 29299326 <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjresp-2017-000215>
12. Hemsley B, Steel J, Sheppard JJ, Malandraki GA, Bryant L, Balandin S. Dying for a Meal: An Integrative Review of Characteristics of Choking Incidents and Recommendations to

- Prevent Fatal and Nonfatal Choking Across Populations. *Am J Speech Lang Pathol.* 2019;28(3):1283–1297. PMID: 31095917 https://doi.org/10.1044/2018_AJSLP-18-0150
13. International Federation of Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies. Red Cross Red Crescent Networks. International First Aid Resuscitation and Education Guidelines. 2020. Available at: https://www.globalfirstaidcentre.org/wpcontent/uploads/2021/02/EN_GFARC_GUIDELINES_2020.pdf [Accessed April 24 2023].
 14. Taniguchi Y, Iwagami M, Sakata N, Watanabe T, Abe K, Tamiya N. Epidemiology of Food Choking Deaths in Japan: Time Trends and Regional Variations. *J Epidemiol.* 2021;31(5):356–360. PMID: 32536639 <https://doi.org/10.2188/jea.JE20200057>
 15. Dodson H, Cook J. Foreign Body Airway Obstruction. StatPearls. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing. Last Update: March 6, 2023. Available at: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK553186/> [Accessed April 24 2023].
 16. Sahin A, Meteroglu F, Eren S, Celik Y. Inhalation of foreign bodies in children: experience of 22 years. *J Trauma Acute Care Surg.* 2013;74(2):658–663. PMID: 23354266 <https://doi.org/10.1097/TA.0b013e3182789520>
 17. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Nonfatal choking-related episodes among children--United States, 2001. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep.* 2002;51(42):945–948. PMID: 12437033
 18. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Toy-related injuries among children and teenagers--United States, 1996. *MMWR Morb Mortal Wkly Rep.* 1997;46(50):1185–1189. PMID: 9414147
 19. State of New Jersey Department of Health. Office of Emergency Medical Services. State of New Jersey Emergency Medical Dispatch Guidecards. 2020. Available at: <https://www.nj.gov/911/home/highlights/EMD%20Guidecards%202020%20Final.pdf> [Accessed April 24 2023].
 19. Landoni G, Morselli F, Silvetti S, Frontera A, Zangrillo A. Pizza in adults and grape in children are the most frequent causes of foreign body airway obstruction in Italy. A national media-based survey. *Resuscitation.* 2020;149:141–142. PMID: 32114069 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resuscitation.2020.02.016>
 20. Salih AM, Alfaki M, Alam-Elhuda DM. Airway foreign bodies: A critical review for a common pediatric emergency. *World J Emerg Med.* 2016;7(1):5–12. PMID: 27006731 <https://doi.org/10.5847/wjem.j.1920-8642.2016.01.001>
 21. Rodrigues AJ, Scussiatto EA, Jacomelli M, et al. Bronchoscopic techniques for removal of foreign bodies in children's airways. *Pediatr Pulmonol.* 2012; 47(1):59–62.
 22. Sahin A, Meteroglu F, Eren S, Celik Y. Inhalation of foreign bodies in children: experience of 22 years. *J Trauma Acute Care Surg.* 2013; 74(2):658–663.
 23. Wang KP, Mehta AC, Turner JF, ed. Flexible bronchoscopy. Hoboken, NJ: Wiley-Blackwell; 2012.
 24. Singh V, Singhal KK. The tools of the trade-uses of flexible bronchoscopy. *Indian J Pediatr.* 2015;82(10):932–937.
 25. Foltran F, Ballali S, Rodriguez H, et al. Inhaled foreign bodies in children: a global perspective on their epidemiological, clinical, and preventive aspects. *Pediatr Pulmonol.* 2013;48(4):344–351.

26. Grassi R, Faggian A, Somma F, et al. Application of imaging guidelines in patients with foreign body ingestion or inhalation: literature review. *Semin Ultrasound CT MR*. 2015;36(1):48–56.
27. Passàli D, Lauriello M, Bellussi L, et al. Foreign body inhalation in children: an update. *Acta Otorhinolaryngol Ital*. 2010;30(1):27–32.
28. Salih AM, Alfaki M, Alam-Elhuda DM. Airway foreign bodies: a critical review for a common pediatric emergency. *World J Emerg Med*. 2016;7(1):5–12.